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HISTORY

TRANSFORMATION OF BAKUNDU-LAND UNDER BRITISH COLONIAL ADMINISTRATION, 1922 - 1960

By

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Abstract

The historical transformation of Bakundu society started during the thirty years of German rule in Cameroon, when the Bakundu were subjected to many external influences that altered their way of thinking and action. The partition of German Cameroon between the British and French after World War One led British to introduce their rule in the British Cameroons. Bakundu encounter with the Germans and later the British colonialists broadened Bakundu horizon in all spheres of human endeavour. This article attempts to survey the developments introduced by the Germans and how the British policies transformed Bakundu society especially in the fields of education, agriculture, trade and social amenities like roads which improved the standard of living of the people. The paper suggest that this was a continuation of the work started by the Germans. The data for the paper was obtained from both primary and secondary sources like oral interviews, archival reports during the period under review.

Key words: **British Rule, transformation, colonial rule, Bakundu land**

Introduction

The people referred to as Bakundu are a Bantu speaking people who inhabit parts of Meme Division in the South West Region of Cameroon. They speak a language known as *Lokundu* which is similar to other coastal language like *Mokwe* among the Bakweri. They are made up of thirty-four villages and are found in two clusters separated by thirty kilometers and are referred to as Northern and Southern Bakundu¹: northern Bakundu is located between longitude 9°8' east Greenwich meridian and between latitudes 4° 55' and 5° 61' north of the equator,² while Southern Bakundu is located between longitude 9°12' and 9°28' and latitudes 4°23' and 4°28' north of the equator.³ The Bakundu share a forest ecology with the Mbonge, Bafo, Balong and the Bakossi ethnic groups and they all refer to 'Ngoe' as their ancestor.⁴ Northern and southern Bakundu are bounded in the

¹ File No AC/61/143/1 VOL.1932 AD. Garson "Re-assessment Report on the Bakundu Tribal Area, Kumba Division" National Archives Buea, hence forth referred to as NAB.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid.

⁴ File No. 143/1631 vol. 2 Reassessment Report of the Bakundu clan in Kumba Division. NAB.

east by the Balong, to the south by the Bakweri and to the west by the Mbonge. Their neighbors to the north are the Ngolo and Balue groups of peoples.

Map showing the Location of Bakundu land in the South-West Region of Cameroon

The geographical spread of the Bakundu homeland had by the nineteenth century been clearly defined after a series of migrations that led to the establishment of permanent settlement administrative changes, the Bakundu ethnic label and territory have remained under changed. They are found today in two administrative units or colonial areas namely, Konye and Mbonge. This description leads us to a discussion on British administration in Bakundu land which was the same as that of their neighbours.

The Beginning of British Influence in Bakundu land

Under the British, British Southern Cameroons was first a League of Nations Mandate attached to Nigeria and later a United Nations Trust Territory. For administrative purposes, it was divided into four divisions: Victoria, Kumba, Mamfe and Bamenda.⁵ Lagos was the seat of government but in 1949, Buea became the sub-regional capital of British Southern Cameroons. Each division was administered by a Divisional Officer (D.O) who reported to the Resident in Buea.⁶ In 1922, the Native Authority Ordinance of Nigeria was extended to British Southern Cameroons and this was the first step towards the introduction of the British *Indirect Rule* Policy in the territory. *Indirect Rule* or Lugardism implied the participation of Africans in the management of their affairs. This system was built on British colonial experience which was basically attributed to Lord Frederick Lugard who had served as British Colonial Governor of Nigeria.⁷ The system did not replace indigenous system of authority but rather ruled through them. In this way, they respected native interest only when they did not clash with theirs.

Implicitly or explicitly, *Indirect Rule* offered a number of advantages to the British. They used African structures of government. They used the peoples' judicial systems like courts where the people presided over than British officials thereby reducing the cost of their administration. On the other hand, Indirect Rule with its reforming and modernizing local norms and formations in conformity with British norms was accepted by the people. In this regard, the British saw their rule as an attempt to "help" the colonized find their own cultural path in the modern world.

To modernize the political field in Bakundu land, the British appointed chiefs where there were no chiefs⁸ like David Ike of Ibemi Bakundu in 1958 to replace Chief Moto Nebo who was already too old to rule. Under the British then, the Bakundu traditional system began experiencing changes especially with the application of Indirect Rule. Having adopted Indirect Rule, the British proceeded to create Native Authorities (N.As) and there were two in Bakundu land, one at Kombone which was created in 1924 for Southern Bakundu and another at Ndoi for the North Bakundu.⁹ These structures were a modified institutional framework for indirect rule and a mechanism for administering law and

⁵ Victor Julius Ngoh, *History of Cameroon since 1800* (Limbe: Presbyterian printing press, 1996), 170

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Joseph B. Ebune, *The Bakundu of Cameroon Yesterday and Today. A study in Tradition and Modernity* (Kansas City: Macmillan academic Publication, 2914), 73

⁸ Cyril Elad Eparch, "The Balkanisation of the Bakundu from pre-colonial to 1922: A Study in Underdevelopment" (M.A thesis, University of Yaounde 1, 2005)

⁹ File No 105/1921 Vol. 1 Reorganization of Native Administration, Kumba Division, NAB.

order in society. The N.As had their own bureaucrats and treasures responsible for collating taxes and all the revenues from taxes and court fines was paid into the central treasury in Kumba.

Native administration in British Southern Cameroons and Bakundu land in particular was based in Nigerian native institution subject to British control to prevent abuses. A number of ordinances was passed to ensure its effectiveness. These included the Native Authority Ordinance, the Native Court ordinance and the Native Revenue Ordinance.¹⁰ Under the 1916 Native Authority Ordinance, a chief was recognized by the government to maintain order and appoint native police to assist in this purpose. Native court ordinance of 1914 and were composed of native judges who administered customary law. On the other hand, Native treasuries based on the Native Revenue Ordinance were responsible for levying taxes and collecting revenue and were to decide how these were to be disbursed.¹¹

Under the neo social and economic order imposed by colonial rule, the Bakundu during Germans and later the British rules, lost their sovereignty which affected their status in society. In this regard, those professions like smiths who were highly respected in society began their place because of European presence as people began adopting European ways. This was also the case of titleholders and members of secret societies who traditionally controlled Bakundu society.

British rule also affected Bakundu society negatively. This foreign rule encouraged disunity among the Bakundu which affected their development however indirectly. In 1931 for example, the Bakundu demanded the creation of separate treasuries which the British refused stating "that it is not thought possible to remove the native treasury from the control of D.O and none of the ten authorities are yet of sufficient importance or capacity to have separate treasuries".¹² However, the real reason for this refusal was the shortage of staff.

The desire by British to foster development within the division was seen in their bid to create the Kumba Federation of the N. As in 1930. A possible reason accounting for the creation of the Federation was to break through the inter-ethnic differences and foster wide group solidarity for the achievement of the goals of social, economic and political growth. On the side of the Bakundu, this was intended to make them think, act and work as a group although they live in two different clusters that were developing independently from each other. In this way, as a limited group they could cope with the completion of their neighbors and kinsmen. On the other hand, it was seen as a desire of harnessing their resources in order to foster development under British rule.

In the light of the foreign the Bakundu under the British were to experience political change which affected traditional political institutions. This transformation was not complete although significant changes had been made with the introduction of British rule. The functions of chiefs were modified which included settlement of disputes at village level, collection of taxes, and reporting diseases. Within this framework of the British Rule, Chiefs became the agents of colonial rule and by so doing gradually lost

¹⁰ Raymond Leslie Bnell, *The Native Problem in Africa* (New York: The Macmillan company, 1928), 688.

¹¹ Ebune, *The Bakundu*, 76

¹² File No 110/17/1932 Kumba Division creation of separate native Treasuries, NAB

their political power and influence. The loss of political authority was however partial because the village and kingship basis of politics did not disappear. Councils of elders continued to meet at night or in secret if necessary and many important matters like marriage transaction, succession and inheritance, even land disputes were resolved without recourse to the colonial state and its agents. Despite all that the British had laid the basic social infrastructures in the area like the building of roads, health facilities and a political system that was to enable the Bakundu to attain rudiment of a modern state.

Economic transformation

Prior to the coming of Europeans to the Cameroon Coast, the Bakundu were agriculturalists who grew food staples like plantains, yams and cassava, cocoyam, a variety of vegetables and sweet potatoes. In addition to farmers, hunters and fishermen also played a role in the traditional Bakundu economy. They also grew oil palm from which they extracted oil. Oil palm was the pioneer export crop early in the nineteenth century and later palm kernels and groundnuts in the second half of the same century.

At this early stage the Bakundu economy has generally been described as subsistence economy although the concept of 'subsistence' is an inadequate characterization of the Bakundu production system. With the development of agriculture, the Bakundu became a 'colonizing' people, expanding their numbers and their territory through migrations. This would not have occurred if the economy was based mainly on subsistent production. Expand and colonies, a society needs to prophase surpluses or more than its own immediate needs.¹³ The existence of such a system in which people specialized in various activities suggests the existence of economic diversity which can be used for other purposes.

Other aspect of the traditional Bakundu economy included hunting, fishing and gathering. Fishing was carried out in fresh water while hunting was limited to small game like hares, monkeys and porcupines. On the other, weaving and wood carving were also important activities of the pre-colonial Bakundu economy. Artisans and craftsmen produced utensils, raffia bags, baskets, stools, hoes and cutlass, all household utensils which were also bartered in local trade. Livestock like goats, sheep, short horned cattle, hogs and poultry were also kept and served diverse purposes like payment of bride wealth.

The Bakundu economy under the British was basically a continuation of what the Germans had started. When Britain assumed effective control of British Southern Cameroons, she gave priority to reviving the economy which had begun to decline at the outbreak of the First World War. Attention was initially focused on agriculture¹⁴ and trade. The economic charges began shifting from subsistence to a modern economy which helped to improve the living standards of the people.

By the 1920s, the demand for cocoa was high and more than half the male population became cocoa farmers. A.D Garson noted that cocoa cultivation became the main occupation of 75% of the Bakundu and in 1930 production reached 98 tons.¹⁵ By the late 1920s a bag of cocoa was sold at 12 shillings. However, there was a drop in the 1930s

¹³ A.G. Hokins, *An Economic History of West Africa* (New York: Longman Group Ltd, 1973), 12-129

¹⁵ File No. 143/1 Vol AGRI A.D. Garson Esq, Reassessment report on the Bakundu Tribal Area, 1931, N.A.B.

perhaps due to the Great Depression. Cocoa and other cash crops like coffee brought a social revolution as seen in the emergence of indigenous wealthy men like Nathaniel Bebe of Banga. Despite the Great Depression that led to a fall in cocoa prices, the Bakundu continued to produce cocoa in growing quantities as shown in the table below.

Table 1: Cocoa farming in Bakundu Villages in 1930

Village	Number of bags	Number of farmers
Ndoi	126	23
Kanye	15	09
Kokaka	18	20
Wone	12	09
Mbakwa	48	29
Kake	140	30
Kombone	122	21
Marimba	81	20
Nake	84	18
Bole	91	22
Foe	12	16
Total	989	207

Source: A.D Garson Esg. ADO Reassessment in the Tribal Area of Bakundu, 1930 N.A.B.

There is no doubt that production of cocoa in Bakundu land increased. This is because by the 1930s, southern Bakundu people had large farms than their counterparts in the north, averaging 5-10 acres.¹⁶ The increased interest in cocoa farming led to the improvement of farming from rudimentary to more advanced ways. One of the ways that this was done was the development of cooperative societies. This contributed for the expansion of not only cocoa, but rubber and coffee farming because they provided a ready and modern means of marketing all produce. The first Cooperative Society in Bakundu land was established in 1932 at Kake and another was created at Kanye. In 1952, a third was established at Banga.¹⁷

The cooperative movement was thus a clear indication of the growing importance of cash crop farming among the Bakundu under British administration. The cooperative began aiding farmers by supplying farm tools like spraying machines. Indeed, the use of machines and applications of chemical to protect the crops against diseases alongside other methods encouraged not only better yields but made many Bakundu to become farmers. Bakundu farmers like Sooe of Boa, Mediko and Samuel Motuba of Kanye and Etoto of Supe were among the first members of the cooperative society.¹⁸

To encourage modern and high yield production, the British colonial administration appointed superintendents of agriculture to supervise the proper use of modern techniques like application of chemicals to protect the crops against diseases. All these

¹⁶ Ebune, *The Bakundu*, 84

¹⁷ File No Qd/a 1953/3, Intelligence Report on the Bakundu Tribe, Kumba Division, Cameroon province, N.A.B.

¹⁸ Ebune, *The Bakundu*, 86

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aimed at promoting high production and a better quality of cocoa which would benefit the Bakundu financially and economically. This development shows the progress of westernization and modernization that was unfolding in Bakundu land under the British.

To modernize agriculture more, the British in October 1927 introduced the native authority cocoa fermenting scheme in Kumba, Mambanda, Kurume, Ikiliwindi, Nyasoso, Baduma and Kombone.¹⁹ One result of all these initiatives was the construction of ovens to properly season the fermented cracked cocoa grains. Harvested cocoa was formerly dried on the barns with fire built under the cocoa beans. The introduction of ovens improved the quality of cocoa and the income earned by the farmers. On the other hand, the rise in income encouraged many Bakundu to become farmers as well as the social status and prestige of those who made more money. One most important result of building ovens by groups and individuals was that kingship and ethnic solidarity strengthen traditional institution and values which were already adapting to and serving modern economic needs. Apart from the role by the British colonial government in fostering economic growth among the Bakundu, Christian Mission like the Basel, the Catholic and Baptist also played a significant role in the transformation of the Bakundu society under European rule.

They introduced new agricultural methods. Their desire was to grow more food to feed the growing population. Furthermore, to encourage agricultural production, seedlings of plants like oranges were distributed to farmers. The new farming techniques employed in the cultivation of these crops had a profound effect on the people as many of them took up cultivation of various crops thereby improving on their diet. Such innovation turned many Bakundu into full time farmers leading to economic diversification which helped to improve on the material circumstances of the Bakundu.

Trade

In Bakundu land, trade was also an important economic activity and the major trade items included palm products, ivory, rubber and cash crops like cocoa. Gun powder, trinkets, pipes, umbrella, mirrors, textiles and liquor were luxuries imported from Europe. The African Fruit Company based in Bombe bought cocoa and palm kernels. Revenue obtained from the sale of these products enabled the Bakundu to purchase European luxuries. One consequence was the gradual neglect and eventual abandonment of many indigenous crafts and arts, a phenomenon that has been noticed elsewhere in Africa.²⁰

The change from barter trade to the use of currency by the Germans and British facilitated exchange. Due to this change, Bakundu villages like Bombe, Banga, Ngongo, Wone and Konye became important market centers. People from other areas came there to sell their

¹⁹ File No Cd/a 1928/V DAR; 1927 Annual Report for Kumba Division, N.A.B.

²⁰ E.A. Akintoye, *Emergent Africa States: Topics in Twentieth Century Africa History* (London: Longman Group, 1926), 82 – 3.

goods and purchased their needs. The presence of two rivers, Meme to the west and Mungo to the east facilitated increasing trade during this period. Increase in trade under the British is shown in table 2 below.

Table 2: Food stuff and livestock prices under British rule

Foodstuff / livestock	Price
Plantains	1 - 1d a bunch
Coco yams	3s per cwt
Egusi	1d a cigarette tin
Goat	8s - 20s according to size
Sheep	8s - 20 according to size
Pig	10s - 30s according to size ²¹

These economic activities created and sustained trade links with other ethnic groups. Under British administration then, there was an improvement in trade which attracted people from northern areas like the Banyang of Manyu division, Hausas from British Northern Cameroons and Nigerians to settle and trade in Bakundu land. Their presence impacted on the local economy as many Bakundu also became traders and raised incomes which improved their standards of living and social welfare. In order not to belabor the point, it is certain that these economic changes had their implications among the Bakundu in various ways. If the Bakundu were yet completely westernized they were nonetheless traditional in their outlook and style. The growing monetization and its social impact was visibly obvious in the existing physical infrastructures modern homes built by some prominent Bakundu farmers such as Bebe of Banga and Mediko of Konye. These structures still dot Bakundu villages even today. They reflect their new lifestyle, testifying in their own way the indelible footprint of British colonial rule which was similar to a education in the broadest sense of the term.

Education

In its educational policy, the British continued from where the Germans ended. German education policy left the task of education in the hands of the mission bodies. In 1922, the British decided that most of the educational effort in due course came under the direct control of mission who are in a better position than the administration to develop disciplined character.²² This was because the missions had already provided the structures and the curriculum for the schools.

When the First World War broke out, most missionaries left British Southern Cameroons because of the hostilities and uncertainty that characterized the period. There was continued by the Basel and German missionaries. Following the historic partition of the former German *Kamerun* by the Anglo-French Agreement in 1916, the British who received 1/5th of the territory, which corresponds to the then recognized territory of

²¹ File No. 143/1 vol ARG1 A.D. Garson Eq. ADO Reassessment Report on the Tribal Area of Bakundu 1931. N.A.B.

²² Dundas and Carr. Re-assessment Report on the Bakundu, N.A.B.

British Southern Cameroons, were fortunate to find Basel mission schools in virtually all major Bakundu villages.²³ The British and the missions worked hand in hand to expand educational opportunities among the Bakundu.

The Lieutenant Governor of the Southern Provinces of Nigeria where the British Southern Cameroons was administered, in his arrival report of education stated that the education of Cameroonians was in the hands of the Basel and Roman Catholic missions who were operating in the territory. The number of the schools managed by the missions continued to rise sharply such that by 1924, the Basel mission had a total of 32 primary schools in the British Southern Cameroons alone.²⁴ The situation was probably the same elsewhere in the British sphere. For example, in Bakundu land within the same period, a school was created at Itoki in the early 1920s which served children from Northern Bakundu villages of Mbua, Ibemi and Koba. The idea of creating schools in villages was of course welcomed by the people and this was in itself a self-campaign that positively impacted on other Bakundu villages to expand educationally. According to Dundas and Carr, between 1922 and 1926, the enrolments in existing schools in Bakundu land between 1922 and 1926 was to an extent impressive as tables 3 below suggests.

Table 3: School Attendance in Selected Bakundu Villages, 1922 - 1926

Villages	Number of pupils
Kombone	40
Banga	40
Kombone and Boa	20
Bole	30
Pete	30
Kake	25
Bopo	15
Ibemi	16
Itoki	25
Konye	20
Kokaka	10
Mbakwa	45
Ndoi	10

Source: Dundas and Carr, Reassessment Report on the Bakundu. NAB.

A new School Ordinance came into force on 26 May 1926 which authorized the government to supervise mission schools. These schools actually lacked several amenities. Evidence suggest that the schools lacked qualified teachers and infrastructures and Lagos had to decide whether to approve or not to approve them. The resident at Buea

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

intervened and the Education Department permitted them to be registered as religious schools to teach reading, writing and religious instruction in the vernacular language.²⁵

Following several appeals from the locales in British Southern Cameroons, the education department in Lagos reorganized the religious schools as proper village schools. The schools and teachers were registered and supervised by the government. To solve the problem of unqualified teachers, those pupils who passed an examination in English were recruited as teachers. Between 1926 and early 1930s, the Basel Mission had improved on the existing old schools and created new ones. Bakundu children who would later become teachers passed out of these schools in the 1930s, 1940s and 1950s like Marvis Efim Ebile and Peter Ekoi who was an acclaimed role model in Bakundu land. Thus, western education became the measuring rod of development in Bakundu land because it steadily liberated the indigenous people from certain repugnant tradition to modern ways of thinking in action as did Christian teaching.

Christianity

Evangelization and conversion into Christianity were the main tools and preoccupation of the missionaries to spread Christianity. These were intended to change the Bakundu outlook to adopt modern ways. The Christian missionaries, the Baptist, Presbyterians and Catholics operated in Bakundu land during the period of British rule. Their mission of conversion began with the social context in which it occurred including the economic interest of the people like farming and trade. This was made easier because Christianity and Bakundu belief system had much in common. The Bakundu, for example, believed in a supernatural being while Christianity teaches about believe in one God. As earlier noted, this made the process of converting the Bakundu easier which was first started by the German missionaries.

The missionaries on the other hand contributed to the well-being of the Bakundu which was as an important factor in the process of conversion. The belief in a supreme deity, love for one's neighbor, the fulfilment of people's economic and social needs were common in Christian and Bakundu belief system. The Bakundu accepted Christian teaching which did not differ much from what they knew was good for them. They were able to grasp the essentials of western Christianity and adopted it as their own without abandoning everything of the old ways.

The missionaries did not only want to convert but to provide the so-called 'civilized' context within which the values of Christianity would best be propagated. This is why the converts they made became agents of positive change throughout Bakundu land. Missionary involvement in the spread of western education, provision of healthcare and other social services signaled a dramatic revolution in traditional Bakundu economy with the result that change became inevitable as more and more Bakundu began adopting western lifestyle. All these changes were possible because the missionaries used the gospel to 'purify' or purge the Bakundu, while laying the groundwork for the colonial

²⁵ W. Keller, J. Schnellbach and R. Brutsch, *The History of the Presbyterian Church in West Cameroon* (Victoria; Press book Printing Press, 1969), 65.

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authorities to easily implant their exploitative administrative policies. In this regard, the colonial authorities provided the needed security to the missionaries to easily carry out their evangelization work in the suburbs.

Conclusion

This essay has shown the role the British played in transforming the Bakundu land social and economic system which they inherited from their German counterparts. Under British administration therefore, the Bakundu economy expanded and social infrastructures were further developed. This led to the greater exposure of the Bakundu to the world beyond theirs, especially through the medium of trade. The provision of western education and new administrative structures broadened their outlook thereby driving them toward more modern approaches in their daily life. It is this fact alone that impacted more as they now competed with their neighbors in pursuit towards modernity. In this vein therefore, the changes first introduced by the Germans and later the British have become irreversible especially under the younger generation of the Bakundu whose desire for positive social, economic and political changes in their mainstream society have increased vividly over time.

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